

Analogs of Tuberin : Syntheses and Biological Activity of Some New 4-Methoxy Styryl Carbamates and 4-Methoxy Styryl Semicarbazones⁺

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Manuscript received 5 February 1977, revised 9 January 1978, accepted 21 March 1978

Analogs of a well known antibiotic, Tuberin, have been synthesised and their antitubercular antibacterial and antifungal activities were studied. Here we report the syntheses of some new 4-Methoxy Styryl Carbamates and 4-Methoxy Styryl Semicarbazones. One of the carbamates was active against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strain and some others showed promising antibacterial and antifungal activities.

ANTITUBERCULAR¹, antibacterial² and fungicidal³ activities associated with Tuberin (N-formyl-*trans*-paramethoxy styryl amine) isolated from broth filtrate of *Streptomyces Amalcosaensis* and its analogs prompted us to synthesise several new structural congeners of potential medicinal interest.

Perusal of literature revealed that very little work has been carried out on the syntheses of the corresponding styryl carbamates and styryl semicarbazones. 4-Methoxy cinnamic acid required in this series was prepared by known method. Preparation of the azide and its decomposition to the isocyanate was done by adopting a modified Curtius method⁴. The isocyanate was converted to the carbamates on treatment with phenolic and alcoholic compounds. 4-Methoxy styryl semicarbazide was prepared by the reaction of the isocyanate with hydrazine hydrate. The semicarbazide on condensation with various aldehydes yielded the semicarbazones. The chemical reactions are represented in Schemes 1 and 2 and the compounds prepared are tabulated in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

The *in vitro* antibacterial, antifungal and antitubercular activities of compounds (1) to (40) were studied by serial dilution technique⁵, using dimethyl formamide as the solvent. Dilutions were made so that in no instance was there more than 1% dimethylformamide in the test medium. At such concentrations dimethyl formamide has no inhibitory effect on the organisms.

Among the compounds tested, (1), (3), (5) and (7) showed very good and promising antibacterial and antifungal activities. Compound (1) a quinolyl derivative was active against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strain at 25 mcg/ml level. This also showed good activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* at 6.25 mcg/ml and had promising results against certain human pathogenic fungi. Synthesis of compound (2), a 5, 7-(dibromo) 8-quinolyl derivative with an idea to increase the activity did not show any promise. Compound (3), an ortho nitro dibromo phenolic derivative showed activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and had weak antifungal activity. However, the para nitro isomer as in compound (4) resulted in total loss of activity. Compound (5), a 4-nitro phenyl substituent showed weak antifungal activity, whereas a 4-nitro benzyl derivative, compound (6) did not show any promise.

Compound (7) with a 4-nitro vinyl phenyl substituent enhanced the antibacterial and antifungal activities considerably and these are shown in Tables 3 and 4. The rest of the compounds did not show any significant activity.

Except for some weak antimicrobial activity exhibited by compound (24) none of the other compounds in Table 2 showed any significant antitubercular, antibacterial or antifungal activity.

Experimental

2-Nitro-4, 6-dibromo phenyl-N-(*p*-methoxy styryl) Carbamate (3)

Paramethoxy cinnamic acid azide (4.2 g, 0.02 mole)

+ Presented before the Annual Convention of Chemists held at Bangalore, December 1976.

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SCHEME-I

SCHEME-II

TABLE-1

Compound No.	R	M.P. °C*	% Nitrogen	
			Found	Calcd.
1.	8-Quinoly-	177-79	8.98	8.75
2.	5-7-Dibromo 8-quinoly-	190-92	5.53	5.80
3.	2-Nitro-4, 6-dibromo phenyl-	98-100	5.96	5.90
4.	4-Nitro-2, 6-dibromo phenyl-	174-76	5.99	5.90
5.	4-Nitro phenyl-	180-82	8.92	8.91
6.	4-Nitro benzyl-	138-40	8.97	8.50
7.	4-Nitro vinyl phenyl-	170-71(d)	8.60	8.20
8.	Benzyl-	116-17	5.35	4.95
9.	4-Chloro benzyl-	156-58	5.00	4.40
10.	4-Methoxy benzyl-	133-35	4.91	4.47
11.	3-Nitro-4-acetamido phenyl-	185-87(d)	12.10	11.32
12.	α-Naphthyl-	168-69	4.88	4.40
13.	β-Naphthyl-	185-86	4.51	4.40
14.	Methyl-	134-36	6.21	6.70

* All melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE-2

Compound No.	R	M.P. °C*	% Found	Analysis Nitrogen	Calcd.
15.	Phenyl-	204-05	14.72		14.23
16.	2-Hydroxy phenyl-	190-92	13.84		13.50
17.	3-Hydroxy phenyl-	193-95	13.60		13.50
18.	4-Hydroxy phenyl-	192-92	13.68		13.50
19.	2-Nitro phenyl-	189-90	16.78		16.47
20.	3-Nitro phenyl-	212-14	16.00		16.47
21.	4-Nitro phenyl-	226-28	16.64		16.47
22.	4-Chloro phenyl-	205-07	12.87		12.72
23.	2-Hydroxy-5-Nitro phenyl-	207-08	15.96		15.70
24.	4-Hydroxy-3-chloro phenyl-	197-98	12.47		12.14
25.	4-Methyl phenyl-	186-88	13.40		13.59
26.	2-Methoxy phenyl-	147-49	13.02		12.92
27.	3-Methoxy phenyl-	200-02	13.06		12.92
28.	3, 4-Dimethoxy phenyl-	195-97	12.18		11.90
29.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxy-5-chloro phenyl-	206-08	11.26		11.17
30.	α -Naphthyl-	201-02	12.21		12.17
31.	β -Naphthyl-	210-11	12.03		12.17
32.	2-Pyridyl-	178-80	18.38		18.92
33.	3-Pyridyl-	186-88	18.15		18.92
34.	4-Pyridyl-	198-200	18.76		18.92
35.	3, 4-Methylenedioxyphenyl-	199-201	12.57		12.40
36.	3-Indolyl-	201-201	16.74		17.20
37.	Cinnamoyl-	202-03	13.11		13.08
38.	2-Furyl-	201-03	15.01		14.74
39.	4-Nitro furyl-	186-87	16.74		17.00
40.	Cyclohexyl-	178-80	14.53		14.63

* All melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE-3

Compound No.	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>Tr. mentagrophytes</i>	<i>M. gypseum</i>	<i>Ph. jeanselmi</i>	<i>N. asteroides</i>	<i>Asp. funigatus</i>
1.	50	6.25	6.25	6.25	—	12.5
2.	50	25	25	50	50	12.50
5.	—	50	50	—	—	—
7.	50	6.25	6.25	6.25	—	25

— No activity below 50 mcg/ml concentration.

TABLE-4

Compound No.	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>A/R.S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. shigae</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>Pr. vulgaris</i>	<i>Ps. aeruginosa</i>	<i>My. tuberculosis</i>
1.	6.25	6.25	—	—	—	—	—	25
3.	12.50	12.50	—	—	—	—	—	—
7.	25	12.50	50	25	25	25	25	—

— No activity below 50 mcg/ml concentration.

was dissolved in dry benzene (50 ml). This was added dropwise to boiling benzene (20 ml) in a 250 ml round bottomed flask kept in an oil bath at 120-130°. After refluxing for an hour, it was cooled to room temperature and -2-nitro-4,6-dibromophenol (5.6 g, 0.02 mole) in dry dioxan (25 ml) was added dropwise with stirring. After 3 hours, the

product was filtered and washed with benzene. It was recrystallised from aqueous dioxan, 98-100°.

(Found : N, 5.90%. Calculated for C₁₆H₁₂O₂N₂, N, 5.99%)

The other compounds listed in Table 2 were prepared in the same manner.

4-Methoxy Styryl Semicarbazide (15)

Paramethoxy cinnamic acid azide (4.2 g; 0.02 mole) is taken in dry benzene (50 ml) and is added in drops to boiling benzene (10 ml) in a round bottomed flask kept in an oil bath at 120-130°. After the addition, it was refluxed for an hour. Hydrazine hydrate (95% ; 5 ml) taken in dry dioxan (20 ml) was added at room temperature with stirring to the isocyanate in benzene. After stirring for about 3 hours, it was kept overnight and the solid that separated was filtered and dried. The product was recrystallised from alcohol. Yield 80%. m.p. 205-207°. (Found : N 19.7%. Calculated for $C_{10}H_{18}N_8O_2$, N, 20.3%).

4-(Paramethoxy styryl)-1-(3-chloro-4-hydroxy benzyl) semicarbazide (24)

(1), (4.13 g, 0.02 mole) dissolved in alcohol (40 ml) was added to 3-chloro-4-hydroxy benzaldehyde (3.2 g, 0.02 mole) in alcohol (50 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (2 ml). On warming the mixed solution the product separated out. It was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried. Yield 90%. m.p. 197-98°. (Found N, 12.47%. Calculated for $C_{17}H_{16}N_8O_3Cl$, N, 12.14%).

The compounds were obtained in an average yield of 85-90% and are reported in Table 2.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. V. Srinivasan, Director, for his encouragement and kind permission to publish this paper. We also thank Mr. C. S. Natarajan and his team for the analytical data.

References

1. K. OKUMA, K. ANZAI and S. SUZUKI, *J. Antibiotics (Tokyo) Ser.*, 1962, A. 15, 115-16.
2. K. ANZAI and S. SUZUKI, *J. Antibiotics (Tokyo) Ser.*, 1962, A. 15, 202-09.
3. K. ANZAI, *J. Antibiotics (Tokyo) Ser.*, 1962, A. 15, 123-29.
4. J. WEINSTOCK, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 3511.
5. "Mackie and McCartney's Hand Book of Bacteriology" (Ed.) R. CRUICKSHANK, E & S Livingstone Limited, Edinburgh, Scotland, 1962, p. 407.